

APPROXIMATE STRESS ANALYSIS OF THE IOSIPESCU SHEAR SPECIMEN

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SUMMARY: Use of higher order beam theories is investigated in conjunction with stress analysis of the Iosipescu (v-notch) shear test for composite materials. Higher order displacements are utilized which lead to a third order polynomial in the thickness coordinate for the inplane normal stress. Through-the-thickness shear and normal stresses are obtained by integrating the equilibrium equations from classical theory of elasticity. This procedure leads to a fourth order polynomial in the thickness coordinate for the transverse shear stress. The shear stress distribution at the notch cross-section as obtained from the higher order beam theory in conjunction with a graphite/epoxy unidirectional composite is compared to an available finite element solution. Discrepancies between these solutions are discussed. In addition, numerical results indicate that the transverse normal strain can have a significant influence on the shear stress distribution at the notch cross-section.

KEYWORDS: inplane shear, interlaminar shear, Iosipescu shear test, shear tests, higher order beam theory, stress analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The V-Notched beam (Iosipescu) shear test is now a standard test method under ASTM D5379. In addition to being widely accepted by the aerospace industry this test method is being utilized by other organizations, such as the Automotive Composites Consortium, as a standard for determining shear strength and modulus. The genesis of this test method can be found in a paper published by Iosipescu [1]. In this paper he proposed the test specimen shown in Fig. 1 for determining the shear properties of metals. Iosipescu argued that a 90° v-notch in the presence of a cross-section with zero moment would produce a state of pure shear which is uniformly distributed across the width, w , between the notches. Because the sides of the notches are parallel to the normal stress direction, Iosipescu also concluded that no stress concentration, at least for isotropic materials, existed at the bottom of the notch.

A considerable amount of work has been done in analyzing the shear stress distribution at the notch cross-section of the Iosipescu shear specimen. Most of these have been accomplished utilizing the finite element method. However, the geometry of the Iosipescu specimen presents a particular challenge to the finite element method. For example, it can be shown that stress distributions in the notch section of the specimen are very much influenced by the stress-free boundary conditions along the notch surface. Conventional finite element formulations, which are usually based on displacements, cannot directly satisfy traction-free boundary conditions, as these are natural conditions to be satisfied in the limit. Other difficulties can be encountered with the finite element method. Further complications arise with regard to stress analysis by the existence of a singularity at the notch tip for certain

material properties and laminate geometries [2]. In addition, load placement and distribution can have an effect on the shear stress at the notch cross-section [3-5].

Fig. 1 : Iosipescu (v-notch) shear specimen

In the present paper two higher order plane stress models are presented for evaluating the stresses in the vicinity of the v-notches in the Iosipescu specimen, including the transverse normal stress. The models are based on an expansion of the displacements in the through-the-thickness coordinate, z , in the same fashion as higher order plate theories are often developed. Governing equations and boundary conditions are obtained from minimizing potential energy. Both approaches yield a third order polynomial in z for the through-the-thickness distribution of the inplane normal stress. Through-the-thickness shear and normal stresses are obtained by integrating the equilibrium equations from classical theory of elasticity.

Fig. 2: Idealized loading with St. Venant effect dissipated

HIGHER ORDER BEAM ANALYSIS

In performing a higher order beam analysis we must assume that there is sufficient distance between the interior loads so that St. Venant's principle applies. In such a case the loading is idealized as shown in Figure 2. Under this condition we can consider a simplified analysis using the free-body diagrams shown in Figure 3. Using the free-body diagram on the left-hand side of Figure 3, we denote the beam depth by $H(x)$. Thus,

$$H(x) = (h-2x) \tag{1}$$

In developing a higher order beam theory applicable to the Iosipescu shear test, we retain the usual assumptions associated with bending loads. In particular, the inplane normal stress, σ_x ,

Fig. 3 : Free-body diagram for analytical model

is assumed to be anti-symmetric with respect to the through-the-thickness coordinate. For the present work we choose a displacement based theory which produces a third order polynomial for σ_x relative to the thickness coordinate, y . If a displacement based formulation is utilized, two approaches can be implemented in obtaining the desired distribution of σ_x . In the first case the effect of the thickness normal strain, ϵ_y , is neglected, which leads to the displacement field:

$$u = y\psi(x) + \frac{y^3}{3} \phi(x), \quad v = v^0(x) \tag{2}$$

These displacements lead to the following normal stress, moment, and shear force resultants

$$\sigma_x = yE_1 \left(\psi_{,x} + \frac{y^2}{3} \phi_{,x} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} M &= t \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \sigma_x y dy = E_1 t \frac{H^3}{12} \left(\psi_{,x} + \frac{H^2}{20} \phi_{,x} \right) \\ Q &= t \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \tau_{xy} dy = G_{12} t H \left(\psi + v_{,x}^0 + \frac{H^2}{12} \phi \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where a comma denotes partial differentiation, t denotes the beam thickness in the z direction, E_1 is the beam modulus in the x -direction, and G_{12} denotes the shear modulus relative to the x - y plane.

If we include the effect of the transverse normal strain, ε_y , the displacements in eq. (2) take the form

$$u = y\psi_{,x}(x) + \frac{y^3}{3} \phi_{,x}(x), \quad v = v^0(x) + \frac{y^2}{2} \psi_{,y}(x) + \frac{y^4}{4} \phi_{,y}(x) \quad (4)$$

which leads to the following normal stress, moment, and shear force resultant

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= y \left(Q_{11} \psi_{,x,x} + Q_{12} \psi_{,y} \right) + y^3 \left(\frac{Q_{11}}{3} \phi_{,x,x} + Q_{12} \phi_{,y} \right) \\ M &= Q_{11} \frac{tH^3}{12} \left[\psi_{,x,x} + \frac{Q_{12}}{Q_{11}} \psi_{,y} + \frac{H^2}{12} \left(\phi_{,x,x} + \frac{Q_{12}}{Q_{11}} \phi_{,y} \right) \right] \\ Q &= G_{12} ht \left[\psi_{,x} + v_{,x}^0 + \frac{H^2}{12} \left(\phi_{,x} + \frac{\psi_{,y,x}}{2} \right) + \frac{H^4}{320} \phi_{,y,x} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where Q_{ij} are the reduced stiffnesses for plane stress.

Equation (4) contains all of the polynomial terms in the y coordinate which contribute to both a third order inplane stress, σ_x , and a fourth order transverse shear stress, τ_{xy} . Integration of the first of eqs. (5) in conjunction with the first equilibrium equation from classical theory of elasticity also produces a fourth order polynomial in y for the transverse shear stress, τ_{xy} . However, the expression for τ_{xy} obtained from assumed kinematic relations does not satisfy appropriate boundary conditions. This can only be accomplished by integrating the first equilibrium equation from classical theory of elasticity with the result

$$\tau_{xy} = - \int_{-H/2}^y \sigma_{x,x} d\zeta + \tau_{xy}(x, -H/2) \quad (6)$$

The second term in this relationship represents the value of τ_{xy} at the top of the cross-section, which in general does not vanish. Stresses relative to the x - y coordinate system along the

free boundary are shown in Fig. 4. These results along with a similar consideration of the lower notch boundary at $y = -H(x)/2$ lead to the conditions

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_y(x, -H/2) &= \sigma_x(x, -H/2), \quad \tau_{xy}(x, -H/2) = \sigma_x(x, -H/2) \\ \sigma_y(x, H/2) &= \sigma_x(x, H/2), \quad \tau_{xy}(x, H/2) = -\sigma_x(x, H/2)\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

A major effect produced by the 90° notch is the introduction of a significant σ_y stress component. In conventional beam problems this stress component is not present except in the vicinity of a vertical surface traction. The distribution of σ_y can now be determined by

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_x, \quad \tau_{xy} = \sigma_x, \quad \sigma_x = \frac{M(x)H(x)}{2I(x)}$$

Fig. 4: Stresses along notch boundary in $x - y$ coordinate system

integrating the second equation of equilibrium from classical theory of elasticity in conjunction with the resulting expression for τ_{xy} as determined from eq. (6), i.e.

$$\sigma_y = - \int_{-H/2}^y \tau_{xy,x} d\zeta + \sigma_y(x, -H/2) \quad (9)$$

It should be noted that eq. (9) will yield a third order polynomial in y when used in conjunction with axial strain effects only, while a fifth order polynomial will result when transverse strain effects are added. If σ_y is determined from kinematic assumptions, the resulting function will be of the same order in y as the corresponding function for σ_x .

For either kinematic relations, eq. (2) or eq. (4), two variables can be eliminated from the analysis by using M and Q as determined from the shear and moment diagrams, i.e.

$$M = \frac{P}{2}(h - w - 2x), \quad Q = -P \quad (10)$$

The remaining equilibrium equations in terms of displacement variables are determined from the principle of minimum potential energy. In order to conserve space the governing equations will not be presented here.

For the case of axial strain only, the governing equations can be reduced to a single non-homogeneous differential equation in the variable ϕ . The resulting solution is of the form

$$\phi = -\frac{420wh^2}{(9 + 35G_{12} / E_1)H^3} + \frac{630w^2h^3}{(9 + 35G_{12} / E_1)H^4} + \frac{A}{H^\lambda} + BH^\lambda \quad (11)$$

where $\pm \lambda$ are the roots of a quadratic equation involving geometric parameters and material properties. The undetermined coefficients A and B are determined from the following boundary conditions

$$\text{At } x=0, \frac{(h-w)}{2}: \quad \phi_{,x} = 0 \quad (12)$$

The variables ψ and v^0 are determined from the moment and shear force in conjunction with eq. (11).

When transverse strain is also included, three non-homogeneous, coupled, differential equations in the variables ϕ_x , ψ_y , and ϕ_y are obtained. In this case the solution is of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_x &= \sum_{i=1}^6 A_i H^{\lambda_i} + L_1 \frac{wh^2}{H^3} + L_2 \frac{wh^3}{H^4} \\ \psi_y &= \sum_{i=1}^6 F_{1i} A_i H^{\lambda_i} + L_3 \frac{wh}{H^2} + L_4 \frac{wh^2}{H^3} \\ \phi_y &= \sum_{i=1}^6 F_{2i} A_i H^{\lambda_i} + L_5 \frac{wh^3}{H^4} + L_6 \frac{wh^4}{H^5} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where L_i are coefficients of a particular solution, while A_i are undetermined coefficients of the homogeneous solution. In addition λ_i are roots of a sixth order polynomial involving geometric parameters and material properties. The coefficients f_{ij} are eigenvector ratios. In this case the boundary conditions are of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \text{At } x=0: \quad & \phi_x = \phi_{x,x} = \phi_y = 0 \\ \text{At } x = \frac{(h-w)}{2}: \quad & \phi_{x,x} = \psi_y = \phi_y = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Conditions at the notch cross-section lead to vanishing of σ_x for both cases under consideration and continuity of v for the second case. Symmetry (or anti-symmetry) as dictated by Figs. 2 and 3 assure continuity of u and τ_{xy} at the notch cross-section. The

boundary conditions at the beginning of the notch region ($x = 0$ in Fig. 3) lead to linear distributions with respect to y for σ_x in both cases and for u in the second case.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

We now consider two examples, a unidirectional composite with the fibers oriented along the x -axis, $[0^\circ]$ composite, and a unidirectional composite with the fibers perpendicular to the x -axis, $[90^\circ]$ composite. Assumed material properties will be those typical of current graphite/epoxy composites. Before displaying the solutions, however, some discussion is in order relative to differences in behavior between these two cases. In particular, solutions for the $[0^\circ]$ case tend to be unstable for two reasons. First, there is a definite effect of assumed load placement and distribution on the stresses at the notch cross-section [3-5]. But even more importantly is the existence of a stress singularity at the notch tip [2]. In the case of $[90^\circ]$ graphite/epoxy unidirectional composites, the notch tip stresses are very insensitive to load placement and distribution [3, 5], and no singularity exists at the notch tip [2].

For the $[0^\circ]$ composite the following material properties are assumed:

$$\frac{E_1}{E_2} = 15.4, \quad \frac{G_{12}}{E_2} = 0.615, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.3 \quad (15)$$

where E_2 is the modulus in the y -direction. Here ν_{12} denotes the major Poisson's ratio as determined from a uniaxial tensile test in the x -direction while measuring contraction in the y -direction. When transverse strain effects are included in the kinematic relations, eq. (4), the reduced stiffnesses can be determined from the relationships

$$Q_{11} = \frac{E_1}{(1 - \nu_{12}^2 E_2 / E_1)}, \quad Q_{12} = \frac{\nu_{12} E_2}{(1 - \nu_{12}^2 E_2 / E_1)} \quad (16)$$

A comparison of shear stress distributions at the notch-tip for the two kinematic assumptions, eqs. (2) and (4), and classical beam theory are shown in Fig. 5. The notch depth is given by $w/h = 0.5$ and shear stress values are normalized by the average shear stress at the notch cross-section, i.e.

$$\tau_{xy}^* = \frac{wt\tau_{xy}}{P} \quad (17)$$

The shear stress distribution is determined from equilibrium consideration, i.e. eq. (6). For the case of a classical beam,

$$\sigma_x = \frac{M(x)y}{I(x)} = \frac{6Py(h-w-2x)}{t(h-2x)^3} \quad (18)$$

where $I(x)$ is the moment of inertia of the cross-section with respect to the z -axis. Substituting this relationship into eq. (6) and performing the integration, we obtain the following expression for transverse shear stress

$$\tau_{xy} = -\frac{3P}{2t(h-2x)^2} [w + 4(2h - 3w - 4x)\left(\frac{y}{h-2x}\right)^2] \quad (19)$$

At the notch cross-section this relationship yields the following normalized shear stress:

$$\tau_{xy}^* = -\frac{3}{2} \left[1 - 4\left(\frac{y}{w}\right)^2 \right] \quad (20)$$

Thus, the beam solution yields a classical parabolic shear stress distribution which is independent of material properties.

Results in Fig. 5 indicate a large effect of transverse normal strain as well as a significant departure from elementary beam theory. In fact these results indicate the type of instability alluded to at the beginning of this section and leaves serious doubt that any of the three cases represents an accurate solution.

For the [90°] composite the material properties relative to the x-y coordinates are as follows:

$$\frac{E_1}{E_2} = 0.065, \quad \frac{G_{12}}{E_2} = 0.04, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.0195 \quad (21)$$

A comparison of models for the shear stress distribution at the notch cross-section is shown in Fig. 6 for $w/h = 0.5$. As in the case of the [0°] composite considerable departure from elementary beam theory is displayed by the higher order theories. However, in this case similar results are obtained with and without transverse strain included. Thus, the solution appears to be more stable than for the case of the [0°] unidirectional composite. In addition, plane stress finite element results from Ref. [4] are included. The ABAQUS and PATRAN codes were used for calculations and pre-, post-processing, respectively.

A large discrepancy is quite evident between the shape of the shear stress distribution in Fig. 6 as obtained from the higher order beam theories and the finite element solution. It is difficult at this point to conclude which one of these two solutions is more accurate. As previously pointed out there are difficulties with the finite element procedure. In particular, a cursory examination of eq. (6) reveals that the boundary condition has a very important role to play in the shear stress distribution. Again, the exact boundary conditions are obtained only in the limit in conjunction with displacement based finite elements. It can be shown that in the absence of a singularity and load effects, which is the situation with the case displayed in Fig. 6, the shear stress at the notch tip must vanish. The finite element solution does not quite vanish at the notch tips. Some discrepancy between these finite element results and moiré data can be found in Ref. [5]. However the shape of the shear stress distribution as obtained from the moiré data is much closer to the finite element results than the higher order beam theory. It should also be noted that moiré data is difficult to interpret in the presence of high strain gradients.

Fig. 5: Shear stress distribution at notch cross-section, $[0^\circ]$ composite

Fig. 6: Shear stress distribution at notch cross-section, $[90^\circ]$ composite

CONCLUSIONS

Results of the present study are inconclusive concerning the applicability of higher order beam theories to the stress analysis of the Iosipescu shear specimen. Because of the absence of a singularity, and insensitivity to load placement and distribution, the [90°] unidirectional graphite/epoxy specimen is ideal for this study.

To aid in resolving the discrepancies observed in Fig. 6, solutions from additional higher order beam theories need to be considered. Displacement based solutions of the following form are appropriate.

$$u = \sum_{i=\text{odd}}^N z^i \psi_x^{(i)}(x), \quad v = v^0(x) + \sum_{i=\text{even}}^{N+1} z^i \psi_x^{(i)}(x) \quad (22)$$

This will lead to an Nth order antisymmetric through-the-thickness distribution of σ_x and an N+1 even ordered distribution of τ_{xy} .

It would also seem appropriate that additional finite element approaches, utilizing other than constant strain elements, need to be explored.

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